

Theatre in Times of Crisis: Redefining Liveness in the Transition to Virtual Theatre Presentations During COVID-19

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Theatre has seen various crises and reshaped its presentation style throughout world history. Theatre has exhibited remarkable resilience and creativity in the face of these challenging circumstances. The Covid-19 pandemic represents a recent public health crisis for the theatre industry. In response to the Covid-19 pandemic, the theatre industry adapted by embracing virtual presentations, moving away from its conventional dependence on physical locations. This study examines theatre practices in various crises and explores how the Covid-19 pandemic redefined the concept of "liveness" in theatrical presentations. The research focuses on the intersection of theatre and public health crises. It discusses the survival and adaptation of the theatrical arts during pandemics.

Before Covid-19, theatre practitioners used physical spaces to showcase their theatre performances. These physical spaces accommodated spectators to view the performances. The physical spaces invited live interaction of spectators with actors and peers during the performances. In these performances, spectators strongly contributed to the success of these performances. During this period, tickets were allowed to sell and it helped theatre productions continue. Theatre practitioners also organised many theatre festivals around the globe. The festivals attracted a large number of spectators. These theatre festivals contributed cultural practice. Thus, theatre performances are part of people's lives across the world.

The theatre history demonstrated the influence of diseases on theatre arts. In these uncertain times, the theatre industry showed resilience, strength, and adaptability. Key times of uncertainty in history that influenced theatre include the Black Death in the 14th century, the plague outbreaks of the 17th century, the Cholera Epidemics of the 19th century, and the Spanish Flu Pandemic spanning from 1918 to 1919.

The bubonic plague, commonly called the Black Death, caused widespread devastation

across Europe and Asia in the 14th century. Despite this devastation, theatre continued to present performances and flourished in numerous forms. One of the best known forms is the cycle plays performed during the Black Death. These plays continued to be presented in France, Germany, and Italy during this devastation (Grange 66). Despite the significant loss of life, the continuation of theatrical activities during the plague likely signified societal desire for cultural and religious expression. Theatre's survival during the plague demonstrated its inherent capacity to adapt and thrive amid epidemics.

However, the resilience of theatre has fluctuated throughout various historical periods. Theatrical resilience demonstrated notable differences during the interruptions caused by epidemics in the 17th century. Examples of these interruptions were observed in London playhouses. These playhouses were shut down frequently and for lengthy periods during plague outbreaks in 1608 and 1625 (Walsh 10). In the 14th century, the Black Death demonstrated public health negligence, but in the 17th century, public health was prioritized over cultural activities. After the 14th century, in the 19th century, the intersection between public health measures and cultural performances protection became more complex.

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In the 19th century, cholera epidemics influenced theatrical performances differently in various regions. During cholera epidemics, some cities given preferences to public health rather than cultural events. Theatres in other cities were used to criticize the government. Due to cholera, Paris closed its performances. However, many popular entertainment venues reopened as the epidemic continued. One of the popular entertainments led to the production of "Les pilules dramatiques, ou le choléra-morbus," (Solomon). This performance was satire and included humour to address social issues associated with the cholera epidemic. This performance demonstrates resilience of theatre during cholera, and it presented progress into a performance tool for social critics during the epidemic.

On the other hand, Vienna pursued a more rigorous approach during the cholera outbreak. The emperor proclaimed that theatres should be closed and adapted as temporary hospitals. This action emphasizes the importance of public health over cultural initiatives. Whereas Vienna undertook the complete repurposing of its theatres, Madrid closed them without further adaptation. Madrid's theatre shutdown complied with public health protocols to prevent illness spread. As it was observed in Madrid, the cholera epidemic thinned theatre attendance in New York. A report by the New York Mirror in 1832 indicated that illness concerns led to declining theatre attendance, even though venues remained open to the public. All these responses emphasize how people prioritize public safety.

The interaction between theatrical arts and public health persisted into the 20th century. The Spanish flu pandemic of 1918–1919 emerged as a major challenge for the global theatre community. Theatres across North America closed as part of efforts to manage the crisis. Across the United States, theatres faced mandatory closures. For instance, in Battle Creek, Michigan, the production of "The Cinderella Girls," a musical comedy by the Marx Brothers, was discontinued after three days of performances (Ristani). The ban on performances weakened the American theatre industry. Performance

closure was not limited to the United States. European nations responded diversely to the Spanish flu. They relied on various strategies to shut down theatre performances during the flu. In Europe, some countries implemented strict theatre shutdowns while others followed more flexible approaches. In Germany, theatre performances were closed. In contrast to Germany, France did not close theatres and cinemas due to public discontent fears. Even as factories in Northern London shut down, London invited the general public to theatres and music halls. The strategies applied in Europe and North America were echoed in other regions during the Spanish flu.

In Asia, there was a broad spectrum of responses to the Spanish flu. Japanese authorities opened cinemas, schools and theatres during the flu. They continued to organise theatre performances without interruption during the flu outbreak. Under British rule, India's response to the Spanish flu was inconsistent. Karachi enforced a three-month shutdown of all cinemas and theatres, whereas a significant number of venues in Bombay stayed open throughout this time. The differences in responses to the Spanish flu emphasize the inconsistency of risk assessment in different regions of Asia.

During the Spanish flu pandemic, New Zealand faced unique challenges. Under Minister of Public Health George Warren Russell, the country adopted a resolute approach by instituting widespread closures. Authorities shut down theatres, cinemas, and various other crowded gathering venues. New Zealand's public health authorities clearly prioritized public health by implementing robust preventative measures.

In the 21st century, the entire world faced significant challenges due to Covid-19. Like other industries, the theatre industry also faced many challenges during the pandemic. Prior to Covid-19, epidemics led to theatre closures. However, the Covid-19 pandemic compelled the theatre industry to adapt to digital technology for presentations. This shift allowed theatres to utilize virtual spaces instead of physical ones during performances. These digital presentations redefined the relationship between spectators and virtual performances. Examining spectators'

engagement in online presentations can help identify new directions for theatre practices.

Virtual adaptations:

In response to the Covid-19 pandemic, governments restricted public gatherings. Consequently, theatres suspended performances in their areas. This cessation led to virtual performances to maintain connections with spectators. The advancement of technology preserved theatre spirit during the Covid-19 crisis. Theatre groups began streaming archived performances using digital platforms, such as YouTube, Facebook, Zoom, and others. Some theatre groups organized online readers' theatres, where actors and spectators members could participate from their homes using digital tools. Some of theatre groups temporarily suspended their performances, waiting for safer conditions before resuming physical productions. As a result of the Covid-19, virtual presentations kept the theatre occupied. Adaptations of virtual presentations enabled performers and spectators to connect through theatre.

However, virtual theatre presentations introduced new challenges, such as financial and technological. During the Covid-19 pandemic, the theatre industry faced financial instability due to reduced ticket sales and increased costs associated with maintaining technologies. As spectators engaged with performances in digital environments, they lacked the immersive experience of live theatre, leading to a decline in spectator numbers. A number of technical glitches interrupted online theatre performances. These technical glitches were primarily associated with two issues: bandwidth limitations and viewers' insufficient digital platform knowledge. These two major issues interrupted online theatre experiences. In some cases, traditional theatre performers kept distance from online theatre performances as they were not familiar with the technology involved with virtual theatre performances. All these challenges led to a decrease in online theatre performances during the Covid-19 crisis.

The Hybrid presentations:

After the pandemic, life did not resume quickly. Many people were scared to go to

public places, and they needed physical distance. Many industries implemented a hybrid work model, where some employees worked from home while others worked at the office. Theatre also adopted hybrid presentations. The hybrid approach to theatrical performances suggests that future theatres may rely on a dual model where spectators can watch performances in theatre buildings or on virtual screens at home. This practice may meet spectators' expectations, as most are too busy to reach the theatre building. Some theatre venues are located far from residential areas, requiring spectators to travel a long distance to watch performances. In such cases, spectators may opt for online platforms to view productions.

While the hybrid theatre presentation model attracts larger spectators, it also presents significant drawbacks. The primary concern is the loss of live theatre experiences when spectators watch performances online. Viewers also lose the immediacy and communal environment during live performances. Furthermore, spectators lose connection with the performance space when watching productions online.

Liveness Reimagined :

Liveness is central to theatrical performances. Traditionally, liveness refers to the immediate and empirical experience of a live theatre performance. It demands the real-time presence of both performers and spectators within a physical space. Liveness encompasses a shared experience and renders each performance unique and unrepeatable. While recorded performances do not occur in real-time, live performances happen in the moment and create a strong connection between performers and spectators. Live performances allow spectators to engage actively with the performance unfolding. It creates a medium for performers and spectators to interact in the same temporal and spatial context. Live performances demonstrate spontaneity and authenticity. Liveness is inherently ephemeral, and the liveness of a performance cannot be replicated in exactly the same way. This ephemeral nature fosters a strong emotional connection between spectators and the performance.

In online theatre performances, spectators engage with a two-dimensional

screen, which alters liveness. In these virtual performances, liveness does not connect with three-dimensional spaces but maintains a connection with temporality. In online engagement, spectators interact minimally with space and do not have spontaneous interactions with the performance as observed in performances in physical spaces. In hybrid presentations, where live theatre is screened virtually, liveness occurs in real-time. Spectators who interact with virtual performances experience physical spectator responses. Here, the spectators engaging with the virtual performance are inspired by the dynamics of the spectators in the physical space. This allows remote spectators to experience a sense of immediacy. However, these spectators do not have the sensory experience of the performance, such as the shared experience of physical spectators. While virtual performances create liveness, they do not maintain the intensity of liveness observed in performances conducted in physical spaces.

When spectators view a theatre performance online, they cannot share physical reactions as they are not physically engaged with the performance. In this case, spectators will interact digitally. These digital interactions may create a form of liveness, which can be reinterpreted in the context of online engagement. Here, liveness can be observed in temporal co-presence rather than physical co-presence. Liveness can be observed through the digital interactions of spectators, such as live chats, polls, and comments. These interactive features demonstrate spectators' engagement with the performance. While these interactions cannot be studied by the performers during the performances, they can influence the experience of other spectators who watch the performance on online platforms.

In the case of hybrid models of performance presentation, spectators may have more inclusive theatre experiences. In this scenario, spectators can be divided into two categories: those who watch the performance in the physical space and those who watch it on a digital platform. Here, the spectators who watch on the digital platform may be

influenced by the responses of the spectators in the physical space. This merging of physical and virtual experiences may represent the future of liveness. These hybrid presentations synthesize physical spaces with digital spaces. Such presentations will allow a larger number of spectators to engage with performances in our busy world.

In conclusion, the theatre industry has demonstrated resilience and adaptability in response to various crises. Covid-19 adapted theatre by shifting from physical to virtual presentations. This shift altered the understanding of liveness in theatrical experiences. The hybrid format of theatrical presentation showcased enhanced accessibility, and it partially preserved the concept of liveness. These hybrid presentations combined digital and physical engagement of the spectators. This study indicates that future theatrical presentations might depend on virtual platforms to reach a larger spectator.

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સમાજ સુધારાની કથા કે છેવટ આદર્શો નિરૂપતાં અનેક નાટકો બોક્સ ઓફિસો છલકાવી દેતાં, છતાં એનાથી સમાજસુધારો થયો કે કેમ એ તો ઝીણવટભર્યો અભ્યાસ માગી લે. તેમ કલાનો એવો પ્રતિબદ્ધ ઉદ્દેશ માનીએ તો પણ, એનો એવો પ્રભાવ પડે કે કેમ, એ પણ તપાસ અને ચર્ચાનો વિષય છે. વિષયો તરીકે કજોડાં, સ્ત્રી-સ્વાતંત્ર્ય, ભ્રષ્ટાચાર, માનવદંભ કે ધર્માધત્તા એ જેટલા પ્રમાણમાં ટ્રેજેડીના નિરૂપણમાં કામ આવે, એટલા જ કે કદાચ એથી વધારે, કોમેડી અને પ્રહસનમાં વધુ નાટ્યાત્મક અને પ્રભાવક બની શકે. આ 'મિથ્યાભિમાન' (દલપતરામ), 'મ્યુનિસિપલ ઇલેક્શન' (ડાહ્યાભાઈ ધોળશાજી) વગેરે નાટકો એનાં તુરત યાદ આવતાં ઉદાહરણો છે. પણ એટલું ચોક્કસ જણાય છે, કે ૧૯મી સદીનો આખો ઉત્તરાર્ધ અને ૨૦મી સદીના શરૂના ચારેક દાયકા સુધી ધમધમતી રહેલી એ રંગભૂમિ જે પ્રેક્ષકો માટે, ગુજરાત અને મુંબઈનાં જે શહેરોમાં, જે પ્રકારની મંચનભૂમિમાં, જે 'અભિનય' નાટકો કરતી હતી એનો અંતિમ ઉદ્દેશ સમાજસુધારો હોઈ શકે નહીં, તેમ એ પ્રેક્ષકો પણ સમાજ સુધારો કેવી રીતે કરવો એ શીખવા કે વિચારવા તો નાટક જોવા નહોતા જ જતા.

પુસ્તક : 'પડદો જાણે ઉઘડતો નથી'માંથી. લે:
હસમુખ બારાડી, પાનાં ૧૯૧+૪, પ્ર. આ. ૨૦૧૦, રૂ. ૨૦૦/-
પ્રાપ્તિસ્થાન શિએયર મીડિયા સેન્ટર.